

Photophysical properties of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in solution

Fuat Bayrakçeken^a, Behzad B. Jomehri^b and Ali Yaman^{c*}

^aDepartment of Electronics Engineering, Yeditepe University, Uskudar 81160, Istanbul, Turkey

^bDepartment of Engineering Physics, ^cDepartment of Physics, Ankara University, Tandogan 06100 Ankara, Turkey

E-mail : ayaman@science.ankara.edu.tr Fax : 90-312-2232395

Manuscript received 21 February 2000, revised 29 September 2000, accepted 8 December 2000

A number of photophysical properties of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene have been measured including the decay parameters of the lowest excited singlet and triplet states. Molecules were excited in a two-step process. In the first step, S_1 is created which undergoes intersystem crossing to T_1 , then T - T absorption creates an excited triplet molecule which returns to the first excited singlet level by intersystem crossing. The recreated first excited singlet state decays back to the ground state by emitting B -type of delayed fluorescence.

Relatively little is known concerning the excited states properties of the molecule 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene (hereafter DBCH). The photophysical properties of DBCH correspond at least in its structure, to 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol, 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-one and the *cis*-isomer of stilbene^{1,2}.

The study of the crystal structure of DBCH showed that the benzyl groups accept hydrogen bonds from a hydroxy and an ethynyl group, one to each face of the ring. All the analytical data support the adsorption mechanism that $(4n+2)\pi$ electron aromaticity can be induced in DBCH^{3,4}. The work reported here was undertaken with the aim of determining the values of a number of photophysical parameters which are of significance to the photochemistry and optical spectroscopy of the excited singlet and triplet states. B -type delayed fluorescence mechanism was reported experimentally for the first time for rubrene⁵. Same transitions were also observed for different organic molecules^{6,7}. For B -type mechanism, DBCH molecules were excited in a two-step process. In the first step an excited singlet S_1 was created, which undergoes intersystem crossing to T_1 , then T - T absorption creates T_2 state. Therefore, T_2 state is responsible for B -type delayed fluorescence, whose decay time is depending on the decay time of T_2 state. It is independent from the decay time of T_1 state.

Results and Discussion

The prompt, delayed fluorescence, phosphorescence emission spectra and triplet-triplet (T - T) absorption spectra

were recorded earlier². Presently, prompt (normal) fluorescence, P -type and B -type delayed fluorescence and lowest triplet state decays in different conditions are reported. The identity of the delayed fluorescence and prompt fluorescence spectra excludes the possibility of the triplet state spectra observed being due to an impurity with a low-lying triplet state. Fig. 1 shows the prompt and delayed fluorescence spectra of DBCH. The peak corresponds to a first excited singlet state having an energy of 3.33 eV. Apparently, the absence of rotation about the double bond has brought about the stability of DBCH. The shape of the fluorescence spectrum is similar to the fluorescence spectrum of 5*H*-

Fig. 1. Prompt and delayed fluorescence spectra of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene (—) prompt fluorescence spectrum of a 2×10^4 M solution in methylcyclohexane at room temperature, excitation wavelength 320 nm; (---) delayed fluorescence spectrum in 20% isopentane–80% methylcyclohexane.

dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-one and 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cyclohepten-5-ol. The only difference is a shift in the peak location by about 10 nm. The Raman scattering was not observed on the fluorescence of DBCH in any solution at room temperature. The decay times of S_1 and T_1 states are influenced by the presence of paramagnetic oxygen, therefore all the experiments were performed for vacuum degassed solutions of DBCH. Table 1 shows the photophysical parameters of DBCH. Figs. 2-4 show prompt, *P*-type and *B*-type

Table 1. Photophysical parameters of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in different solutions

Solution	<i>T-T</i> abs. peak nm	Decay of T_1 ns	Prompt flu. ns	<i>P</i> -type del. flu. ns	<i>B</i> -type del. flu. ns
Cyclohexane	425	185 ± 5	9 ± 1	17 ± 5	21 ± 5
20% Isopentane-80% methylcyclohexane	425	-	5.8 ± 0.3	-	-
Ethanol	430	220 ± 5	7 ± 1	15 ± 5	22 ± 5
Methanol	430	215 ± 5	6 ± 1	16 ± 5	20 ± 5
Benzene	440	247 ± 5	11 ± 1	20 ± 5	26 ± 5

delayed fluorescence decays in cyclohexane at room temperature. The decay times were found to be 9 ± 1, 17 ± 1, and 21 ± 1 ns for prompt, *P*-type, and *B*-type delayed fluorescence, respectively. Fig. 5 shows the lowest triplet state T_1 , decay of DBCH at 425 nm; the decay time was determined to be 185 ± 5 ns in cyclohexane at room temperature. Fig. 6 shows the *T-T* absorption spectrum of DBCH in cyclohexane at room temperature. All types of delayed fluo-

Fig. 2. Prompt fluorescence decay of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in cyclohexane at room temperature.

rescence involve a metastable state which is first converted to the first excited singlet state before emitting. It was deduced that *E*-type of delayed fluorescence was produced by

Fig. 3. *P*-type delayed fluorescence decay of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in cyclohexane at room temperature.

thermal activation of molecules from the lowest triplet level to the first excited singlet level. *P*-type of delayed fluorescence is produced by *T-T* annihilation and its decay time depends on the lifetime of T_1 state. *R*-type of delayed fluorescence requires ejection of an electron as a first step and would therefore be expected to occur preferentially by excitation with high energy quanta. After the collision of free electron and positively charged molecule, one can create S_1 state, then *R*-type delayed fluorescence can be observed. In

Fig. 4. *B*-type delayed fluorescence decay of 5*H*-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in cyclohexane at room temperature.

this mechanism T_1 state is not responsible for the delayed fluorescence. For *B*-type delayed fluorescence case, we pump optical energy twice. In the first step we create T_1 state of the molecule and in the second step we create T_2 state by *T-T* absorption, therefore for *B*-type, T_2 state is responsible for the delayed fluorescence via S_1 state. The decay time of *B*-type delayed fluorescence is independent of the lifetime

Fig. 5. Lowest triplet state decay of 5H-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in cyclohexane at room temperature; optical path of cell = 0.2 cm.

Fig. 6. Triplet-triplet absorption spectrum of 5H-dibenzo[*a,d*]cycloheptene in cyclohexane at room temperature.

of T_1 state. We could not record the $T_2 \rightarrow T_1$ fluorescence decays due to the noisy signals and low transition probability. The decay time of prompt fluorescence depends on the lifetime of S_1 state and the environmental conditions (i.e. solvent effect, temperature, impurities, paramagnetic oxygen quenching etc.). Any delayed fluorescence lifetime is longer than the normal (prompt) fluorescence lifetime. The decay times for *P* and *R* types depend upon the probabilities of collision.

Experimental

DBCH (Aldrich) was purified in a high vacuum system (10^{-7} Torr background pressure) before use. All other solvents were also A.R. grade and used as received. DBCH solutions at a concentration of 2×10^{-5} M, were prepared in different solvents at room temperature. The singlet and triplet transient phenomena were excited with a laser flash photolysis set-up described earlier³. Flash experiments were carried out in oxygen free solutions, contained in $1 \times 1 \times 0.2$ cm³ quartz cells with the absorbed light passing along the 0.2 cm path-length. To distinguish the lifetimes of the delayed fluorescences same technique was used as reported earlier^{5,6}.

References

1. A. Yaman, A. B. Bayrakçeken, O. J. Demir, E. Kavlaçoğlu and F. Bayrakçeken, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **76**, 487; E. Kavlaçoğlu, A. Yaman and F. Bayrakçeken, *Spectrochim. Acta, Part A*, 2000, **56**, 1117.
2. A. R. Watkins and F. Bayrakçeken, *J. Lumin.*, 1980, **21**, 239.
3. J. Steiner, E. B. Starikov and M. Tamm, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1996, 67.
4. M. C. Etter, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1990, **23**, 120; P. Wan, D. Budac and E. Krogh, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1990, 255.
5. F. Bayrakçeken, *J. Lumin.*, 1992, **54**, 29.
6. F. Bayrakçeken, *Spectrosc. Lett.*, 1996, **29**, 1579.
7. F. Bayrakçeken, B. Barış, O. J. Demir and A. Çavuş, *Spectrosc. Lett.*, 1996, **29**, 151.